

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY MODULE VII

FROM METHODS TO EVIDENCE: INSIGHTS FROM CASE STUDIES

Highlights Report

Introduction

As the Tools4CAP project enters its final year, the Academy is becoming a central platform for consolidating, disseminating, and operationalising the knowledge generated over the past three years. Its purpose is to guide participants through a structured learning journey that progressively deepens understanding, showcases practical applications, and supports Member States in adapting the lessons learned to their own national contexts.

To achieve this ambition, the Academy, coordinated by the [European Association for Innovation in Local Development \(AEIDL\)](#), adopts a progressive and interconnected three-module structure in 2026. Each module has a distinct purpose, while all contribute to a single, coherent pathway that mirrors the analytical depth of the 12 case studies (CSs) developed within Tools4CAP. This design ensures **continuity and diversity of perspectives, strengthening the project's impact as it approaches completion.** Across the three modules, participants will move from understanding the project's evidence base, to examining real implementation experiences, and finally to reflecting on how Tools4CAP outputs can be applied in their own national contexts.

ORGANISER:

17 MARCH 2026

ONLINE

44 PARTICIPANTS from 18 COUNTRIES

(Public authorities, governance bodies; researchers; innovators; and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector)

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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Held on **17 March 2026**, Module VII brought together more than 40 participants from 18 Member States. The session opened with an overview of project results and the 2026 roadmap, **setting the scene for the Academy's final year learning cycle**. The four case studies presented in this module showcased a set of advanced technical features that distinguish them from the broader group, including the use of sophisticated quantitative modelling, high levels of data integration and interoperability, and strong analytical depth to support **evidence-based decision-making**.

[Tools4CAP Academy](#) aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer – learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet the end users' needs. [Tools4CAP](#), coordinated by ECORYS, is a project embedded in the Horizon Programme that involves 21 partner organisations from 18 EU countries with outstanding expertise in economic, environmental, climate and social issues, new data sources and monitoring technologies, as well as in stakeholder engagement, social, environmental, and animal welfare-related data and indicators, in agricultural and rural development contexts.

CAP Strategic Plans and the use of tools: a Tools4CAP overview

Tools4CAP has made progress in supporting evidence-based strategic planning by developing, testing, and assessing a wide range of analytical, participatory and monitoring tools across Member States. By December 2025, the project had generated a comprehensive set of insights on how these tools can strengthen the design, implementation, and review of CAP Strategic Plans, **particularly in a context where future governance frameworks may grant Member States greater autonomy and flexibility in policy design**.

Building on this analytical work, the project has also formulated recommendations for the next **Multiannual Financial Framework**. These are presented in the **policy brief “CAP 2028–2034: Navigating change for an evidence-based policy”**, published in December 2025, which outlines the implications of the proposed governance shift and highlights the essential role of robust analytical tools, harmonised data systems, and strengthened institutional capacity to safeguard transparency, comparability, and evidence-based decision-making across the Union.

The recommendations included in the analysis present a coherent set of priorities for policymakers at both EU and national levels, as well as for the research community. They underline **the importance of grounding NRPPs and CAP chapters in robust evidence and inclusive processes**, strengthening analytical and data capacities, and ensuring coherence and accountability within a more flexible governance framework. All recommendations can be consulted in [full in the policy brief](#) and will be further refined through insights emerging from the case studies and the project's final year of work.

Lessons learned. Contribution of Tools4CAP case studies

Ilona Rac

University of Ljubljana

The Tools4CAP [case studies](#) show how analytical, participatory and monitoring tools can reinforce the design, implementation and review of CAP Strategic Plans. Across 12 national examples, the project tested quantitative models, participatory decision support methods, monitoring solutions, and integrated combinations of tools, generating practical insights into their added value, operational requirements, and relevance for evidence-based policymaking

The [analysis](#), presented by Ilona Rac (University of Ljubljana), builds on the full set of case study materials completed by November 2025, including tool selection and benchmarking, methodological foundations for each tool group, and the preparation and implementation of the case studies. The assessment draws on both practical and theoretical insights associated with each tool, selected from [a broader inventory](#) based on end user interest and national priorities.

QUALITATIVE AND PARTICIPATORY METHODS

- Germany - IOI matrix
- Ireland - Intervention logic
- Poland - Prioritisation tool

QUANTITATIVE MODELS

- Czechia - GLOBIOM model
- France - Experimental evaluation tool
- Hungary - CAPRI model

DATA AND MONITORING SYSTEMS

- Greece - Policy monitoring tool
- Italy - Policy monitoring tool
- Spain - SOC indicator map

INTEGRAL TOOL (MULTI-TOOL APPROACHES)

- Netherlands - Joint eco-scheme/Farmdyn/AGMEMOD farm income models, IOI matrix, Policy monitoring tool
- Slovenia - Participatory vision building, Policy monitoring tool, Scenario building
- Spain - Digital Farm Book and CAPRI

Tools4CAP case studies by tool category

The evaluation triangulates information from case study insights, exchanges with national partners, and internal project discussions, including a dedicated workshop that validated the findings and deepened the understanding of tool performance in real policy contexts. It followed a structured **five-step approach**:

1. CS reports were produced to document implementation experiences, benefits, limitations, and risks.
2. CS were grouped into four categories reflecting their methodological characteristics.
3. An evaluation matrix was defined with 5 criteria and 12 sub-criteria.
4. Each tool category was assessed by answering a set of evaluation questions.
5. Conclusions and recommendations were developed to guide the use of tools in Member States.

A central component of the assessment is the **Tuneup Evaluation Framework (TEF)**, which provides a conceptual and methodological basis for analysing tools used in the design and monitoring of CAP Strategic Plans. The TEF relies on a categorisation of tools, an evaluation matrix with criteria, sub-criteria, and guiding questions, and the triangulation of evidence from diverse sources. While the criteria and sub-criteria are consistent across all tool categories, the evaluation questions are tailored to the specific methodological and technical characteristics of each type of tool.

The TEF is structured around five criteria: **accuracy, reliability, applicability, accessibility, and efficiency**.

The five criteria of the Tuneup Evaluation Framework

Together, these criteria provide a comprehensive basis for assessing the strengths and limitations of tools, identifying the conditions for their effective use, and supporting Member States in selecting and implementing tools that can enhance the quality and robustness of CAP strategic planning.

The review of evidence across the different analytical tools highlights that **no single instrument can effectively support all stages of the policy cycle**. Instead, each tool offers specific strengths at particular moments, making complementarity essential. When combined, integrated tools and methods can offer substantial strategic value.

Tool	Advantages	Challenges
Models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ex-ante policy simulation Captures production–market–environment interactions High scientific credibility Strong for complex trade-offs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data-intensive Limited on emerging issues High expertise needs Slow vs. policy timelines
Experimental economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Behavioural insights Tests design options (payments, requirements) Complements modelling High rigour and scientific credibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource- and time-intensive Complex methods Hard to align with policy timelines Requires specialised expertise
Participatory tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong stakeholder engagement Supports strategic planning Flexible Low technical barriers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dependent on participation Risk of biases Limited analytical depth Needs skilled facilitation
Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enables performance-based governance Integrates multiple data sources Dashboards clarify outcomes Strong long-term value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutional/legal barriers High initial IT/data investments Data access issue
Integrated case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility Comprehensive analysis Suited to complex challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High entry barriers Requires long-term collaboration

Overview of the advantages and challenges of the methods and tools analysed across the case studies

By contrast, **participatory approaches tend to be the easiest to implement** and can enhance legitimacy and stakeholder ownership, while **more innovative methods**—such as **Earth Observation** and **machine learning applications and UML** (Unified Modelling Language)—hold considerable promise for improving analytical depth and timeliness. However, these advanced approaches continue to face significant barriers, especially regarding data access, interoperability, quality and technical skills.

Overall, the effectiveness of all tools depends heavily on **strong analytical capacity, reliable data infrastructures, and institutionalised collaboration between scientific and policy communities**. Although the technical feasibility of these tools is generally high, their uptake remains constrained by institutional capacity limitations, data gaps, shortages of specialised expertise, tight timelines during CSP preparation, and, in some cases, limited demand for analytical support.

Quantitative tools: the four case studies

The four case studies presented during Module VII demonstrate how modelling and experimental economics can support CAP strategic planning by **assessing policy impacts, testing behavioural responses, and improving the evidence base for decision-making**.

CZ – Assessing CAP policy impacts with GLOBIOM
Juliana Arbelaez (Czechglobe)

The Czech case study applied the **GLOBIOM model** to evaluate the economic and environmental effects of different CAP policy configurations under varying climate scenarios. The analysis shows that environmental conditionalities (GAEC) are critical for maintaining permanent grassland and reducing greenhouse gas emissions, while direct payments may increase emissions from certain crops. The study highlights the **high resource requirements of large-scale models and the need for permanent partnerships** between ministries, model developers, and national research institutions to ensure long-term usability.

HU – Using CAPRI to analyse support for protein crops
Zsolt Szabo (AKI - IEA)

Hungary used the **CAPRI model** to examine how increasing coupled support for soybeans could affect production, land use, farm income and emissions. Scenarios involving higher payments or stricter hectare limits significantly increased soybean output (by up to 160%) and farm income (by up to 80%), while reducing CO₂ emissions in eco-scheme scenarios. The study confirms **CAPRI's suitability for ex-ante CAP analysis at the national level but also reveals limited institutional demand for quantitative assessments** and a strong dependence on model developers for more advanced applications.

FR – Experimental economics to improve AECMs design
Pauline Mace (Oréade-Brèche)

The French case study explored experimental tools—initially a Discrete Choice Experiment, later adapted to the Theory of Planned Behaviour—to better understand the low level of farmer participation in an agri-environmental climate measure promoting protein autonomy. Results show that farmers value environmental and production-related benefits but face financial and time constraints. They also **prefer voluntary rather than mandatory technical support and call for simplified administration and faster payments**. The study demonstrates the potential of experimental economics for ex-ante measure design, while noting that resource demands and small sample sizes may limit applicability in real-world policy processes.

ES – Integrating Digital Farm Book (FMIS) data into CAPRI for pesticide analysis
David Nafria (ITACyL)

Spain tested whether pesticide use data from the Digital Farm Book (FMIS) could improve CAPRI's capacity to assess pesticide-related policies. Incorporating FMIS data produced more realistic pesticide use patterns, better reflecting regional agronomic conditions and eco-scheme incentives. However, voluntary reporting limits data representativeness. The study therefore recommends **mandatory and harmonised Digital Farm Book reporting, supported by anonymisation, validation, and farmer-friendly procedures**, to strengthen evidence-based policymaking and enhance model robustness.

From methods to evidence: insights from Case Studies.

Roundtable summary

The roundtable discussions, moderated by **Professor Emil Erjavec** (University of Ljubljana), highlighted the increasing importance of quantitative and experimental tools in shaping agricultural policy across Europe.

One of the central themes was **the capacity of quantitative models to facilitate structured dialogue among stakeholders with diverse and sometimes conflicting priorities**. By providing a shared analytical framework, these tools help align the perspectives of farmers, sectoral ministries, environmental authorities, and other actors. This function is particularly relevant in the context of the Common Agricultural Policy, where the European Commission relies on quantitative evidence. Strengthening national analytical capacity, therefore, enhances both internal coordination and the ability of Member States to articulate their priorities during negotiations.

The discussions also underscored that **the effectiveness of these tools depends on the availability of robust, high-quality data**. Demand for detailed information is increasing, especially on environmental indicators, biodiversity, animal welfare, and the social aspects of farming. In this context, meeting this demand also requires sustained investment, technical expertise, and institutional commitment. For that reason, a key challenge is encouraging farmers to share data, as they typically provide information only when required or when they perceive clear benefits, while concerns about increased administrative scrutiny remain a barrier. **Building trust, ensuring transparency, and guaranteeing strong data protection are essential to improving data availability and supporting evidence-based policymaking.**

Another important point addressed during the roundtable was **the technical complexity of advanced modelling tools**. Although many models are publicly accessible, their effective implementation requires specialised knowledge, particularly for calibration and operational use. It was highlighted that research institutions are often better positioned than government bodies to host and maintain these tools, as they can provide continuity, technical capacity, and scientific credibility. Moreover, scientific publications resulting from model use help legitimise the findings and increase interest among policymakers.

The role of experimental economics was also examined. While this field generates high-quality scientific outputs and valuable insights into farmer behaviour, its direct influence on policy remains limited. Even experimental methods, which are often designed for academic contexts, do not always align with institutional needs or policy timelines, and results may be difficult for managing authorities to interpret or apply. There is, therefore, **a need to adapt dissemination practices and develop approaches that preserve scientific rigour while making insights more accessible, timely, and relevant for policy processes**. Lastly, limited awareness among governments about the existence and potential of these tools further constrains their uptake.

The discussion also highlighted the potential of **digital farm books**. These datasets offer detailed insights into farming practices, including machinery use, timing of operations, and parcel-level decisions. **Such information can help policymakers better assess the degree of flexibility farmers retain when facing regulatory requirements**, for example, in relation to pesticide restrictions. National

registries of agricultural product purchases provide an additional source of accurate data, although linking these records to specific crops and application periods remains technically complex.

Across all discussions, a common conclusion emerged: although researchers produce robust tools and high-quality evidence, their integration into policymaking remains limited. **In many European administrations, evidence-based decision-making is not yet fully embedded, and political considerations often take precedence over technical analysis.** As a result,

research groups need to take the initiative to demonstrate the practical value of their tools and to ensure that outputs are timely and accessible within policy cycles.

Overall, **progress in the use of quantitative and experimental tools depends on sustained investment in data and analytical capacity, stronger collaboration between scientific and institutional communities,** and deliberate efforts to build trust with farmers and other stakeholders. When these elements align, such tools can significantly enhance the design, evaluation, and implementation of agricultural policies.

Key messages

- Strengthen national analytical capacity to improve both internal coordination and negotiation power with EU institutions.
- Invest in data infrastructure and ensure long-term support for environmental, social, and farm-level data collection.
- Build trust with farmers through transparency, incentives, and strong data protection frameworks.
- Support research institutions as key hosts of complex modelling tools and as bridges between science and policy.
- Adapt scientific outputs—especially from experimental economics—to make them more accessible, timely, and actionable for policymakers.
- Increase awareness within governments about the availability and potential of quantitative and experimental tools.
- Promote closer collaboration between scientific communities and institutions to ensure that robust evidence informs policy decisions.

Workcloud summarising the session

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

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New training modules of the Academy will be published in the near future, [here](#).

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